

1 **PDE6D is a differently expressed gene in cancer.**

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3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 Phosphodiesterases are attractive therapeutic targets in cancer because in general their function is less
8 likely to be required for cellular viability in normal cells as compared to other genes tumors produce in high
9 quantity. Their requirement for cellular viability together with their differential expression based on
10 quantitative determination of therapeutic index suggests their potential importance as adjunctive
11 therapeutics. We measured whole transcription in the human solid tumor in the lungs, the brain, the
12 breast, and organs of the trunk for therapeutic target discovery. We identified the phosphodiesterase
13 enzyme PDE6D as a therapeutic vulnerability in human cancer based on conserved differential expression
14 across tissues. Cancers in which PDE6D was robustly or significantly over-expressed included luminal A
15 breast cancer and pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma (PDAC). In genetically engineered mouse models of
16 cancer in the breast, PDE6D was selectively expressed in p53 ^{-/-} cancers.